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FORMATION OF INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF AN ENTERPRISE BASED ON ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGES

For effective development and compliance with existing trends, an enterprise must constantly improve its activities, which will allow it to adapt to changes occurring in the external environment. Changes that significantly affect the activities of an enterprise and bring it to a new level of development, allow the introduction of new technologies, expansion of the range of manufactured products and services provided, require significant investments that the enterprise may not have. This creates the need to attract additional investment resources from external sources of financing. Investment resources can be attracted by an enterprise with a high level of investment attractiveness, for the formation of which the existing internal resources of the enterprise are used.

The article considers the indicators characterizing the resource potential for investment activities in the Russian Federation as a whole, as well as the structure of investment resources and investments by various features, which allows identifying cleaved trends in investment processes and directions of enterprise development for which it is necessary to attract investment resources. The constituent elements of investment attractiveness are studied and the necessity of implementing organizational changes in order to form and increase the level of investment attractiveness is substantiated.

The possibility of implementing organizational changes in the enterprise's activities without financial costs, due to the internal resources available to the enterprise, not related to monetary and financial ones, is characterized. Due to such changes, the enterprise achieves high performance indicators of its activities, increases its investment attractiveness and attracts investors, thus receiving investment resources for implementing larger-scale organizational changes.

I.

*

	2018 .	2019 .	2020 .	2021 .	2022 .	2022/ 2021, %	2022/ 2018, %
-	210 941	349 731	362 192	400 243	427 395	6,78	102,61
,	108 769	120 058	135 483	161 088	182 451	13,26	67,74
	76,2	75,4	74,9	75,3	74,9	-0,53	-1,71
-	149 762	148 814	144 575	147 575	148 965	0,94	-0,53
-	3 950	4 051	4 175	4 175	4 195	0,48	6,20
,	3 693,1	3 871,5	3 999,4	4 582,4	4 934,5	7,68	33,61
-	45 255,7	49 129,2	48 510,9	67 080,6	81 227,6	21,09	79,49
,	12 400,3	16 632,5	13 418,8	33 915,8	22 313,6	-34,2	79,94
(33 138,2	35 233,1	35 933,6	39 933,8	44 936,7	12,53	35,60

*

[16, . 16-18]

2018 2022 . 79,49 %,
) 79,94 %.

35,6 %.

(
()

2.

2

47,2 % 2018 52,5 %

2.) *

	2018 .	2019 .	2020 .	2021 .	2021/ 2020, %	2021/ 2018, %	2021 - 2018
	56,9	51,6	52,5	61,9	17,90	8,79	5
	47,2	47,3	50,4	52,5	4,17	11,23	5,3
	9,7	4,3	2,1	9,4	347,62	-3,09	-0,3
	0,6	1,0	0,9	1,7	88,89	183,33	1,1
	17,8	19,3	36,0	17,5	-51,39	-1,69	-0,3
	24,7	28,1	10,6	18,9	78,30	-23,48	-5,8

* [16. . 16]

2021 , 2,1% 2020 . 9,4% 2021 .
 —17,8% 17,5% , 2020 2018 2021 .
 36,0%.
 10,6% (2020 .) 28,1% (2019 .), 2021 18,9%.
 — 0,6% 1,7% 2021 .

2.

52,8 56%

. 2.

([16. . 42])

(9,8 % 11,2 %),
 (15,3 % 2018 . 20,4 % 2022 .), (7,1 % 11,9 %).

.3.
 , % ([16, .40])
 3,
 .
 55 % 2018 . 50,2 % 2021 . 54,1 % 2022 .
 — 29,5 % 2018 . 35,2 % 2021 . 32,2 % 2022 .
 2022 . 15,7 % 2020 . 13,7 %

[18].

1)

2)

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

7.

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